

Chemical and size fractionation of particulate matter near a ferromanganese plant to assess its oxidative potential

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Particulate matter (PM) oxidative potential (OP) has recently been considered a better health-based metric of PM exposure than PM mass concentration (Bates et al., 2019). However, there is no clear consensus on the sensitivity of different OP assays to PM properties (such as size fraction and chemical composition) and emission sources. Manganese (Mn) is a major contributor to OP (Gao et al., 2020). However, to our knowledge, the sensitivity of OP assays to Mn in PM in areas with high Mn levels has not been studied so far.

This study analyzes three different acellular OP assays (ascorbic acid (AA), dithiothreitol (DTT) and 2,7-dichlorofluorescein (DCFH)) and their sensitivity to the chemical composition of PM samples of different sizes (PM_{2.5}, PM_{10-2.5}) collected in an industrial-urban area. Urban samples from a nearby area were also collected for comparison purposes. High concentrations of Mn in PM mainly characterize the industrial area, due to the proximity of a ferromanganese alloy plant. The filters of the two size fractions were subjected to a chemical fractionation procedure and analyzed for soluble (in a phosphate buffer solution) and insoluble concentrations of 39 elements by ICP-MS. This approach allowed us to assess the bioaccessibility of the elements and to increase their selectivity as source tracers (Canepari et al., 2019). Data on the ferromanganese plant production rate during sampling were also available. Spearman correlations and principal component analysis (PCA) were performed on the data obtained in the different size and solubility fractions of PM to identify the main tracers of the ferromanganese plant and other sources that contribute to local PM levels and OP values near the industrial source of Mn.

Table 1. Spearman correlation coefficients between OP, PM, and soluble Mn according to the particle size.

	PM _{10-2.5}			PM _{2.5}		
	OP ^{DTT} _v	OP ^{AA} _v	OP ^{DCFH} _v	OP ^{DTT} _v	OP ^{AA} _v	OP ^{DCFH} _v
Mass concentration (µg/m ³)	0.12	0.34	0.05	0.29	-0.02	0.21
Mn soluble concentration (ng/m ³)	0.93	0.47	0.85	0.80	0.18	0.54
OP ^{DCFH} _v (nmol H ₂ O ₂ /m ³)	0.76	0.18		0.57	0.50	
OP ^{AA} _v (nmol/min/m ³)	0.54			0.53		

The correlation coefficients between the OP values determined by the three assays, the mass concentrations of PM_{2.5} and PM_{10-2.5}, and the concentration of soluble Mn in the studied industrial-urban area are shown in Table 1. The correlation coefficients change with the size fraction; the highest

values were found between soluble Mn and OP^{DTT} and OP^{DCFH} in the coarse fraction, and soluble Mn and OP^{DTT} in the fine fraction. In the coarse fraction, OP^{DTT} and OP^{DCFH} were found to be well correlated, while OP^{AA} seems to be poorly correlated with the other assays.

PCA revealed that the largest variance in the dataset (PC1, 41.2%) is explained by the higher content of all elements in PM_{2.5}. However, from Figure 1, we can observe that a smaller portion of the variance (PC2/PC3, 25.6%) is explained by the different element concentrations in the two size and solubility fractions of PM due to different contributions of three main emission sources: industrial emissions (group A) releasing Mn and other elements in soluble PM; traffic (group b) emitting elements from abrasion of vehicle brakes; soil dust (group c) releasing crustal elements. OP^{DTT} and OP^{DCFH} assays predominantly respond to PM emitted from the ferromanganese plant. In particular, they are particularly sensitive to soluble Mn. The emission of these elements in PM depends on the ferromanganese plant production rate during sampling and does not lead to an increase in PM mass concentration, which mainly depends on urban sources.

Figure 1. Biplot of PC2/PC3 from the PCA performed on the studied dataset.

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